

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

OUTCOMES AND FUTURE PROSPECTS FOR THE ECONOMIC AND TECHNOLOGICAL INTEGRATION OF GEORGIA WITH THE EUROPEAN UNION

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Abstract

This article examines the current issues surrounding the economic, cultural, and technological integration between Georgia and European countries. It delves into Georgia's multifaceted relationship with European civilization from a historical perspective, highlighting the country's ambitious and intensive efforts towards integration into the European space, particularly concerning economic, technological, and judicial reforms. The article also announces the decision made on December 14, 2023, regarding Georgia's candidacy for membership in the European Union. Additionally, it outlines the strategic challenges that need to be addressed in the future. Special emphasis is placed on Georgia's geostrategic position, which is increasingly important for connecting transit routes and energy resources between Europe and Asia, particularly through the "Middle Corridor" initiative.

Purpose: This article investigates Georgia's multifaceted acceleration towards economic, cultural, and socio-legal integration within the broader cultural, economic, and geopolitical context of European civilization. It also examines Georgia's contemporary engagement with European and Asian countries, particularly focusing on economic-political and "green" energy-logistics cooperation, and explores prospects for future development and enhancement.

Research Methods: The utilization of interdisciplinary scientific methods, including problem-chronological and historical-genetic approaches.

Keywords: Integration, association, harmony, internet, infrastructural-tour, transformation, hub.

Introduction

Despite the South Caucasus region's status as an intercultural zone, deeply intertwined with both European and Asian civilizations, Georgia's historical trajectory has been marked by a notable development in its adoption of Christian religion and the Roman-Germanic legal system over centuries. This evolution, coupled with its cultural-economic alignment towards the European Union and active engagement in "green" energy-logistics cooperation with European and Asian partners, has significantly amplified Georgia's orientation towards European society, yielding substantial benefits.

In the face of considerable external challenges, Georgia has consistently upheld a symbiotic relationship with European and Asian civilizations. Dating back to the 2nd century BC, the Great Silk Road functioned as a pivotal transcontinental trade network linking China with the regions surrounding the Black and Mediterranean Seas. This thoroughfare facilitated extensive economic and cultural exchanges between the East and West, driving transformations in production and fostering rich cultural interactions. Moreover, it served as a conduit for diplomatic relations between Asia and Europe, notably connecting the Georgian city of Poti with Byzantium and Rome. [1; 34]

During the 2nd century AD, the relationship between Kartli (present-day Georgia) and the Roman Empire was so robust that Emperor Antoninus Pius honored the visit of Kartli's King Pharsman II to Rome by erecting his equestrian statue in the Square of Mars. [2; 233] Similarly, in the eastern reaches of Georgia, the

Kingdom of Iberia actively collaborated with the Roman Empire.

In the 4th century AD, Christianity, originating from Europe, was officially recognized as the state religion of Georgia, marking a pivotal moment in its cultural and religious landscape. [2; 555]

Since the 10th century AD, the holy mountain of Athos, situated on the Chalcidion peninsula in Greece, has served as the oldest and most significant center of ancient Georgian writing and cultural activities. This center was overseen by distinguished Georgian clerics, namely Ekvtime and Giorgi Mtatsmindeli. Under their guidance, new manuscripts were produced, Byzantine literary works were translated, and documents were copied, laying the foundation for the dissemination of Georgian literary works on the global stage. [1; 229]

In the 17th century AD, Sulhan-Saba Orbeliani, a prominent Georgian public figure, collaborated with Vakhtang VI, the king of Kartli, to undertake a diplomatic mission aimed at establishing political relations. Orbeliani ventured into various European countries, including France and Italy, yet his diplomatic efforts ultimately proved unsuccessful. [3; 558]

Following the annexation of the first republic of Georgia by Soviet Russia in 1921, the leadership of the Democratic Republic of Georgia sought political asylum and reluctantly left the country due to political pressures, relocating to France, notably Davi Lévi. Many Georgian intellectuals and cultural figures pursued education in Europe, contributing to Georgia's promotion. Noteworthy examples include the philologist and linguist K. Kapanadze (also known as K. Chan-

turia), who studied in France; the writer K. Gamsakhurdia, who studied in Germany; the historian M. Tamrashvili, who studied in Italy; the artist L. Gudiashvili, who studied in France; and the composer Z. Sotkilava, who studied in Italy, among others.

Furthermore, it is evident that Georgia's engagement with Europe was reciprocated, as Europe also demonstrated interest in Georgia. This acknowledgment is underscored by the Greek Argonauts' maritime expedition to Colchis (Eastern Georgia) in search of the Golden Fleece, a narrative that inspired Apollonius Rhodius's poem "Argonautica" and Euripides's renowned play "Medea," emblematic of classical antiquity's greatest tragedies.

European travelers, including Marco Polo, Don Arcangelo Lambertini, Alexander Dumas (senior), Don Cristoforo de Castellam, and John Sharden, among others, vividly portrayed their experiences in Georgia through their published works.

In Georgia, particularly in Tbilisi, numerous socio-cultural residences and residential buildings bear the architectural imprint of European architects such as Paul Stern from Germany, Alexander Szymanowski from Poland, Giovanni Bernardazzi from Switzerland, and Giovanni Scudieri from Italy, among others.

This historical trend persists today, as Georgia actively participates in the socio-cultural life of Europe through various avenues:

- Georgia became a member of the Council of Europe in 1999, aligning with its principles of human rights, democracy, and the rule of law. The Council of Europe maintains an office in Georgia.
- The country engages in numerous European conferences, notably the Bologna process, aimed at harmonizing higher education across Europe. Georgian youth benefit from exchange programs, mobility schemes, and scholarships under this initiative.
- Georgian scholars and intellectuals contribute actively to scientific publications in prestigious European journals and participate in international conferences and discussions.
- Georgian scientists undertake research projects funded by European educational and scientific authorities. Notable examples include physicist G. Dvali works in Switzerland, neurophysiologist T. Gloveli in Germany, physicist T. Lomtadze in Italy, aviation constructor D. Datashvili in Germany, physicist V. Kartvelishvili in the UK, and others.
- Georgian literary works are regularly presented in Europe, alongside festivals showcasing Georgian national-cultural productions such as wine, musical concerts, and theatrical performances.
- Georgia's sporting community participates actively in European championships, with athletes achieving notable success in various disciplines, contributing to the country's sporting achievements (e.g., L. Talakhadze, European Weightlifting Champion, V. Lipartelian, European Judo Champion, Georgian national football team qualified for the 2024 European Championship, etc.).

The scientific and cultural-economic cooperation between Georgia and Europe is expected to continue

developing, fostering innovative integration with European civilization and ensuring the country's sustainable development and national security.

Furthermore, global economic integration trends indicate that, apart from the US, the main trade, financial, and informational flows are distributed among European and Asian countries [4; 12]. The European Union's interest in cooperation with Asian countries, particularly China, in initiatives like the "One Belt, One Road" project, underscores China's pivotal role in improving transport communications and trade connections between Europe and Asia.

In this context, Georgia's strategic geopolitical position, coastal ports, and transit corridors significantly increase its chances of actively engaging in global economic cooperation. These assets could facilitate the transit of goods from Europe to Asia via both sea and continental routes, thereby reducing transportation costs, intermediary fees, and establishment expenses.

Main Text

The Georgians, with their distinctive traditions, historical heritage, and contemporary identity, form an integral component of European civilization. Recognizing the rapid progression of European societies, our country actively embraces its natural and cultural legacy. Following a period marked by significant geopolitical shifts, a momentous decision was reached by the European Union on December 14, 2023, bestowing upon Georgia the status of a candidate for membership. This decision opens unprecedented avenues for integration into European civilization.

The burgeoning sense of responsibility pervades Georgia at every level.

How does European civilization contribute to our civilization?

European civilization enriches our own through its commitment to democracy, freedom, education, and opportunities, its protection of human rights, dissemination of scientific knowledge, promotion of dynamism, development, modernization, innovation, and technological progress.

What is the significance of Georgia's integration into the European Union?

The integration of Georgia into the European Union holds profound significance. Positioned strategically in one of the world's most geopolitically critical regions, Georgia has historically influenced the connections between Europe and Asia. Driven by its resolve to strengthen bonds with the community of nations, Georgia, owing to its geographical location, historical background, political significance, and economic potential, has emerged as a new focal point in the Eurasian landscape. Consequently, its geostrategic positioning underscores a commitment to integration within European frameworks and intensified political-economic collaboration with both regional and transatlantic partners.

In Georgia, the constitutionally mandated commitment to integration into the European Union and the North Atlantic Treaty Organization (NATO) underscores the country's steadfast dedication to aligning with European values and security frameworks. [5]

Moreover, according to numerous sociological surveys, the prevailing sentiment among the country's populace (exceeding 85%) is in favor of Georgia's integration into the European community.

It is anticipated that, within the framework of the criteria for attaining candidate status in the European Union, akin to the trajectories observed in Poland and Romania, Georgia's economic metrics pertinent to integration will witness significant enhancement. These metrics encompass foreign trade revenues, direct foreign investments, technical assistance, among others.

Presently, Georgia stands as an economically growing nation. Its aggregate gross domestic product per capita is approximated at \$8165. As per the Economic Freedom Index, registering at 68.7 points, Georgia occupies the 35th position among 176 nations globally and ranks 21st among European states (with a

global average score of 59.3 and a European average of 68.2).

Since attaining independence in 1991, Georgia has actively engaged with European frameworks, as well as with European and Asian nations. Noteworthy among these engagements are the following key events: [7]

1. In 1993, at the behest of the European Union in Brussels, the "TRACECA" initiative was launched, aimed at establishing a transcontinental trade and transport corridor. Initially endorsed by 8 nations (Georgia, Azerbaijan, Armenia, Turkey, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, and Uzbekistan), this project garnered the participation of an additional 7 countries in subsequent years (Ukraine, Moldova, Mongolia, Bulgaria, Turkey, Romania, and Iran). (See Figure 1)

Fig. 1. The Europe-Caucasus-Asia Transport Corridor (TRACECA)

Since its inception, TRACECA has emerged as a primary conduit for bridging Europe and Asia. Participating nations actively collaborate to synchronize infrastructure enhancements and economic activities under the project's purview. Driven by persistent geopolitical imperatives, its relevance continues to escalate.

2. The European Union Delegation has maintained operational presence in Georgia since 2008.

3. The European initiative titled "Harmonization of Digital Markets" (HDM), initiated in 2014, endeavors to streamline digital markets, digital economy, and digital society in alignment with the European Union's framework across Eastern Partnership countries, including Georgia. This initiative entails harmonizing and integrating national ICT policies, administrative frameworks, and technological systems through collaborative endeavors.

Consequently, the EU4Digital initiative has been instituted to address key thematic domains such as "eSkills," "ICT Innovation," "Trust and Security in Electronic Identification, Public Services, Information, and Cybersecurity," "eTrade," "Regulatory Bodies for Electronic Communications (Telecom)," and "eHealth" networks. These thematic areas are earmarked for development and harmonization with European Union member states, guided by predefined operational strategies and high-level infrastructure development plans. The Ministry of Economy and Sustainable Development of Georgia spearheads coordination efforts, ensuring comprehensive national participation.

4. The Association Agreement (AA) between the European Union and Georgia, enforced since 2016, incorporates a Deep and Comprehensive Free Trade Area (DCFTA) agreement. This agreement engenders eco-

nommic integration mechanisms with the European Union, thereby opening Georgia's internal market to European Union member states. Apart from fostering free trade, the DCFTA promotes service trade liberalization and addresses a spectrum of trade-related issues such as intellectual property rights protection, competition policy, financial services, among others. Furthermore, it envisages the gradual alignment of Georgia's legislation with that of the European Union in trade-related domains. The DCFTA extends the opportunity for Georgia to progressively avail itself of the four freedoms of the European Union's internal market, encompassing the free movement of goods, services, capital, and persons, establishing a pathway for liberalizing the visa regime.

5. Since 2017, Georgian citizens have been granted visa-free access to the Schengen Zone. The European Union stands as Georgia's principal trading partner, rendering substantial technical and financial assistance annually, disbursing an average of over €100 million to Georgia. [9]

6. Georgia commenced the implementation of a comprehensive national program for fiber-optic and broadband infrastructure development in 2016 with European Union assistance. This program aims to enhance high-speed internet accessibility, facilitating the construction of public networks by major operators and extending internet connectivity to subscribers. Consequently, digital programs and services have become more accessible to the populace, encompassing electronic security, e-learning, e-governance, e-commerce, among others.

7. The implementation of the "National Action Plan for the Development of Georgia's Fiber-Optic Net-

works for 2020-2025" underscores the criticality of fiber-optic infrastructure for the country's sustainable development. This strategy entails an assessment of the prevailing situation and delineates three strategic objectives: 1) Strengthening competitiveness, comprising four sub-objectives; 2) Augmenting investment, encompassing two sub-objectives; and 3) Enhancing digital capabilities and demands, inclusive of three sub-objectives.

8. Under the auspices and financial backing of the European Union amounting to €11 million, a three-year program titled "EU4Digital: Support for the Digital Economy and Society in Eastern Partnership Countries" (comprising Azerbaijan, Belarus, Moldova, Georgia, Armenia, and Ukraine) was executed between 2019 and 2022.

This initiative was geared towards fostering the development of the digital market, streamlining digital infrastructures, and fortifying cybersecurity measures. It envisaged augmenting digital competencies and fostering employment opportunities within the populace, mitigating extant barriers through the provision of online services, streamlining investment objectives, and promoting startup initiatives.

The program encompasses six EU4Digital networks, namely Telecommunications, Cybersecurity and Resilience, Digital Trade, Technological Innovations, Health, and Digital Assets.

Presently, the second phase of this EU-funded four-year program (spanning 2022-2025) is in progress.

Concurrently, additional projects are being implemented under the same initiative, including EU4Digital: Cybersecurity EAST, aimed at bolstering cybersecurity and fostering the uptake of digital services. Furthermore, EU4Digital: EaPConnect endeavors to enhance network infrastructure and services across the Eastern Partnership region, facilitating collaboration between academic, research, and educational communities within the region and the European Union.

9. The European Commission's initiative in 2021, "Priorities for Eastern Partnership Cooperation," underscores the support for digital transformation, entailing a €2.3 million investment scheme aimed at catalyzing post-pandemic recovery and fostering long-term development across Eastern Partnership countries, including Georgia. This investment endeavor is geared towards revitalizing the socio-economic landscape and fostering sustainable development within the region.

10. Georgia's participation in the European Commission's 2021 initiative, "Digital Compass – Package of Digital Principles" (Europe's Path to Digital Decade), is aimed at steering towards a more robust digital Europe by 2030. [9]

11. Facilitated by support from the European Commission, Georgia's internetization endeavors continue to thrive. The number of broadband internet subscribers is anticipated to soar into the millions by 2023. Over the past triennium, within the framework of the national internetization program, projects worth 53 million GEL have been successfully implemented. Notably, the construction of an optical-fiber corridor spanning over 800 km has been completed, linking up to

1000 villages to the internet, encompassing highland settlements. Remarkably, Georgia stands as the inaugural country in the South Caucasus region where Elon Musk's high-speed satellite internet service, Starlink, has been made accessible.

12. The European Union (EU) stands as Georgia's primary contributor to financial support, facilitating the nation's socio-economic development and reformative endeavors. Through the Neighbourhood, Development and International Cooperation Instrument (NDICI), the EU extends both financial aid and technical assistance. It is anticipated that the funding earmarked for Georgia for the 2021-2024 period will amount to €340 million. The designated focus areas encompass the economy, institutional enhancement, legislative refinement, security augmentation, environmental conservation, climate resilience, digital modernization, gender parity, and societal inclusivity. [10]

In the initial nine months of 2023, investments from EU member states totaled \$540 million, with exports to the EU reaching \$669 million, constituting 12% of Georgia's aggregate exports. Moreover, various initiatives aimed at fostering closer alignment with Europe are concurrently underway:

- Over the past five years, Tbilisi has been the host city for consecutive international digital connectivity summits, convening representatives from Europe, the Caucasus, and Asia. These gatherings are centered on cultivating an interregional digital corridor.

- Georgia's potential lies in the full exploitation of a telecommunication digital transit corridor (hub) connecting Asian and European nations. This initiative entails the establishment of international broadband telecommunication internet connections traversing Georgia and the establishment of regional data exchange centers within the country by prominent content providers.

- Forecasts indicate that the global internet connection market in Eurasia will witness an annual growth rate of approximately 30% over the ensuing five years. Given this trajectory, Georgia is strategically positioned to actively engage in the international market via the Black Sea route. Furthermore, the subaquatic linkage across the Black Sea is poised to serve as a foundational element for the development of a digital transit corridor bridging Europe and Asia.

These collective endeavors are poised to catalyze the digital transformation of the region by facilitating the extensive digitization of conventional enterprises, augmenting the expertise within the information and communications technology (ICT) sector, nurturing an environment conducive to innovation, fostering the establishment of novel technological ventures, enhancing both public and private services, attracting supplementary investments, and stimulating industrial expansion on both local and international scales.

In Georgia and its adjacent nations, ongoing deliberations revolve around the Trans-Caspian International Transport Route (TITR), commonly referred to as the "Middle Corridor." This envisioned route is slated to interlink China, Kazakhstan, Azerbaijan, Georgia, Turkey, and Eastern European countries, circumventing the Russian Federation. (Figure 2)

Fig. 2. Trans-Caspian International Transport Route ("Middle Corridor")

In light of the ongoing Russia-Ukraine conflict, the significance of the "Middle Corridor" has escalated significantly. For instance, in 2023, the volume of cargo transported along this route amounted to 2.7 million tons, marking an 86% surge compared to the preceding year. Projections indicate that its capacity is poised to expand to 10 million tons by 2025. The "Middle Corridor" route entails the involvement of 25 companies hailing from 11 countries. Georgia is steadfastly committed to enhancing the efficiency of the "Middle Corridor," a transformation that hinges on active support from the European Union. [11]

Presently, efforts are underway to modernize Georgian Railways, a pivotal component of the "Middle Corridor." This initiative, slated for completion in 2024, aims to elevate the annual capacity of Georgian Railways from 27 million to 48 million tons. [12]

In response to the identified shortcomings and extant challenges facing the "Middle Corridor," the Government of Georgia has ratified the "National Strategy for Transport and Logistics of Georgia 2023-2030" through Decree #315 issued on August 15, 2023. This

strategy delineates a long-term vision along with goals and objectives aimed at fostering Georgia's evolution into a regional transport and logistics hub.

Georgia stands poised to assume a pivotal role within the transit corridor of the South Caucasus region, particularly in realizing profound integration into the international transport and logistics frameworks of Europe and Asia, thereby catalyzing the nation's economic advancement.

Noteworthy pipelines traverse Georgian territory, including the Baku-Tbilisi-Erzurum/Shah Deniz pipeline, the Baku-Supsa pipeline, the Baku-Tbilisi-Ceyhan pipeline, the North-South Main Gas Pipeline linking Mozdok in Russia to Armenia via Georgia, and the Trans Adriatic Pipeline (TAP) (Refer to Figure 3). The TAP facilitates the transportation of natural gas from Azerbaijan to Europe via Georgia and Turkey, bifurcating into two directions: 1) Bulgaria and Central Europe, and 2) Greece and Southern Italy. These pipelines not only serve as a significant revenue stream for the Georgian budget but also underscore the country's security assurances. [12]

Fig. 3. Trans Adriatic Pipeline [13]

Despite a decline in the volume of cargo passing through Georgia's ports and terminals in recent years, attributed to ongoing hostilities in Ukraine and sanctions imposed against Russia, there has been a notable surge in demand for cargo transportation via Georgia's transit routes. [12]

Since June 27, 2023, a direct and regular passenger-cargo ferry service has been operational between the city of Poti (Georgia) and the city of Constanța (Romania), serving as the eastern maritime gateway of the European Union. This route stands as the shortest link

connecting the countries of the South Caucasus and Central Asia to Europe. With no viable alternatives, it is poised to play a pivotal role in the advancement of the Trans-Caspian International Transport Route, commonly referred to as the "Middle Corridor" (Figure 4).

The initiation of the development of the Black Sea Anaklia Deepwater Port will significantly bolster Georgia's maritime capacities. Commencing in 2024, the process of selecting a construction company will commence, followed by the actual construction of the port. The state will retain a 51% ownership stake, while the

remaining shares will be open for investment. The Anaklia port project serves to further enhance Georgia's maritime capabilities and competitiveness, particularly when compared to rival projects associated with the "Middle Corridor." In this context, the importance of the Baku-Tbilisi-Kars (BTK) railway project is underscored. This railway project, operational since 2017, in-

cludes a 98 km segment connecting Kars to Akhalkalaki, with 68 km in Turkish territory and 30 km in Georgian territory. The construction of the Georgian segment was financed by Azerbaijan through two concessional loans totaling \$775 million. Scheduled for completion in 2024, the BTK railway will have a capacity to handle cargo of up to 5 million tons. [15]

Fig. 4. Poti (Georgia) - Constanța (Romania) Passenger-Cargo Ferry Line [14]

China has initiated the "One Belt, One Road" slogan, aiming to enhance transcontinental communications and trade connections in Eurasia. This initiative necessitates the modernization of infrastructure, transportation routes, and simplification of trade procedures. [16; 299] It is noteworthy that China's initiative extends beyond transportation and encompasses broader economic considerations. [17; 5]

Organized by the European Union, Brussels hosted the high-level investor forum titled "Global Gateway" on January 29, 2024. This forum evaluated the potential of the trans-Caspian transport route as the most promising route for improving transportation connections between Europe and Central Asia.

The establishment of the Middle Corridor Multimodal LTD, a unified company for the railways of Georgia, Azerbaijan, and Kazakhstan, signifies a significant step towards regional cooperation and logistical optimization. This joint venture aims to streamline logistical processes and enhance efficiency in the region.

Georgia actively participates in panel discussions within the framework of the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development's (OECD) Eurasia Week. During the panel discussions held in Paris from December 12 to 14, 2023, Georgia's unique position was highlighted, underscoring its significant advantage as a regional logistics and transit hub, particularly in the context of the "Silk Road."

In collaboration with Azerbaijan, Georgia has been involved in the ambitious "Digital Silk Road" project since 2018. This project aims to establish optical-fiber-based telecommunication infrastructure, connecting the countries to Europe in the west and Central and South Asia in the east. The goal is to enhance the digital ecosystem of the South Caucasus region in alignment with global standards. Optical-fiber cables are already being manufactured in Azerbaijan, and the construction of the first phase of the submarine cable line across the Caspian Sea has commenced. [18]

The Digital Silk Way project aims to establish data centers and internet traffic exchange points in Azerbaijan and Georgia, positioning them as global hyperscale centers for data processing. These centers will offer services such as data processing and storage, aiming to reduce reliance on external internet service providers. The project seeks to enhance access to digital services for 1.8 billion people in Central and South Asia and stimulate economic growth. Moreover, it is expected to contribute to the development of data storage and processing infrastructure between Asia and Europe, creating new opportunities for digital businesses and strengthening trade-economic connections.

As part of this initiative, AzerTelecom company has partnered with counterparts in Kazakhstan to lay a 340 km-long, 400-terabit-capacity optical-fiber submarine cable across the Caspian Sea, connecting Sumgait in Azerbaijan and Aktau in Kazakhstan. This infrastructure, known as the Trans-Caspian Fiber Optic (TCFO) cable, aims to interconnect segments of the Digital Silk Way route. [18]

In the second phase, a cable connection is planned between Siyazan, Azerbaijan, and Turkmenbashi, Turkmenistan, in collaboration with Turkmentelecom company. This connection will route internet traffic from Europe to Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan, Afghanistan, Pakistan, and India.

In Azerbaijan, AzerTelecom and the State Agency for Azerbaijan's Regional Development "Azerbaijan Highway" are laying submarine optical-fiber cables along the coastal areas of the Caspian Sea. This network enhances the country's digital infrastructure and internet connections with neighboring countries, facilitating the transmission of multi-terabit data and fostering the telecommunications sector.

Furthermore, on December 17, 2022, a memorandum of understanding was signed in Bucharest among the governments of Azerbaijan, Georgia, Romania, and Hungary, with the participation of the European Commission, on strategic cooperation in "green" energy

production and distribution. This partnership is part of the European segment of the Digital Silk Way route, involving optical-fiber infrastructure between Romania and Georgia across the Black Sea. With a €2.3 billion

investment from the European Union, the project is scheduled to commence in 2024, connecting Georgia to Europe. [19] (Figure 5)

Fig. 5. Black Sea Submarine Cable for Electrical and Optical-Fiber Communications

Caucasus Online, a telecommunications company, manages the strategic energy infrastructure in Georgia, which includes a 1200-kilometer subsea cable and a 95-kilometer terrestrial cable with a transmission capacity of 2 terabits per second, expandable to 16 terabits.

Through participation in the Black Sea submarine electricity cable project, Georgia aims to become a transit corridor and exporter of electricity, establishing itself as a key player in the European Energy Community. This project will facilitate the transmission of electricity between the shores of the Black Sea, supporting Georgia's transition to an electricity hub and integration of its electricity market with the European Energy Community.

The strategic geographical positioning of Georgia endows it with the potential to serve as a pivotal hub linking Europe and Asia. This advantageous location has spurred discussions with transcontinental telecommunications operators, who have expressed keen interest in establishing a presence in the South Caucasus region and contributing to the development of global "data centers." This engagement is expected to stimulate competitive pricing dynamics in the domestic internet market, enhance service quality, mitigate the impact of natural disasters, facilitate access to digital content, and bolster Georgia's role in redirecting telecommunications traffic between Europe and Asia.

As the "Digital Silk Road" project progresses and the network interconnection components are modernized, a key challenge will be the consolidation of these elements into a centralized management structure within a unified network. This entails harmonizing communication protocols, encryption standards, and content delivery mechanisms to align with the objectives of global domain providers.

Supported by financial backing from the European Union, the "Do IT with the EU" initiative has been underway since 2020, aiming to stimulate innovation and workforce development in Georgia's IT sector. Over the course of two years, the project intends to train more than 1300 individuals for highly sought-after and lucra-

tively compensated professions, including cybersecurity, data science, cloud computing, and project management. Additionally, 1000 IT professionals will have the opportunity to obtain international certifications, while 300 individuals will receive specialized employment opportunities to enhance Georgia's competitiveness in the global market. [20]

Georgia has implemented effective measures to attract international IT companies, offering significant tax incentives such as a 5% income tax and a 5% corporate tax. Consequently, over 100 international IT firms are presently operating in the country, including notable entities like Rakuten, Viber, Epam, Lineate, etc.

In line with European Union directives, the 3E-Partnership initiative, a comprehensive three-year project launched this year, seeks to bolster regional cooperation in renewable energy and energy efficiency sectors. The project aims to facilitate institutional development and foster innovative knowledge exchange, with active involvement from European partners in Belgium, Italy, and Spain.

Moreover, the Council of Europe unveiled its fourth action plan for Georgia for the period 2024-2027 on January 18, 2024. This plan is designed to align the country with European values and standards, reinforcing human rights, the rule of law, and democratic principles. These measures are expected to support the implementation of democratic reforms in Georgia, further aligning legislation and institutional frameworks with European norms. [21]

Considering its historical trajectory and current geostrategic considerations, Georgia appears firmly oriented towards integration into European civilization. These collective endeavors offer promising prospects for Georgia to commence negotiations on EU membership, a matter slated for discussion at the European Council summit in December 2024.

In the interim, we are confronted with substantial and labor-intensive tasks ahead. Principally, we must address the nine-point agenda delineated by the European Commission, which encompasses:

1. Combatting disinformation pertaining to the EU and its underlying values.
2. Enhancing Georgia's alignment with the EU's foreign and security policy.
3. Mitigating political polarization.
4. Ensuring the integrity of electoral processes by fostering free, fair, and competitive elections and finalizing electoral reforms.
5. Further bolstering parliamentary oversight, particularly concerning security services, and safeguarding the institutional autonomy and impartiality of key entities, notably the election administration, the National Bank, and the Communications Regulatory Commission.
6. Concluding and implementing reforms within the judiciary.
7. Ensuring the efficacy, autonomy, and impartiality of institutions such as the Anti-Corruption Bureau, the Special Investigation Service, and the Personal Data Protection Service.
8. Enhancing the existing action plan for de-oligarchization.
9. Strengthening human rights protections, including through the implementation of a robust human rights strategy and guaranteeing freedom of assembly and expression.

Conclusion:

Reflecting on the centuries-long economic and cultural interactions between Georgia and European nations yields several insights:

1. Historically, the economic and cultural connection between Georgia and Europe was largely sporadic and fragmented. Europe exhibited relatively limited interest in the South Caucasus region, including Georgia. Despite Georgia's proactive engagement, external influences from hostile entities such as the Ottoman, Persian, Mongol, Russian empires, and Arabs hindered its full integration into European civilization.
2. Since attaining independence, Europe's perception of Georgia has undergone a fundamental shift. Georgia's strategic location in the South Caucasus, particularly as a vital node in the "Middle Corridor," has heightened its significance as a conduit between Europe and Asia, circumventing the confrontational stance of Russia. Concurrently, Europe has emerged as a dependable guarantor of Georgia's enhanced independence, fostering a trajectory characterized by security, sustainability, innovation, democracy, freedom, education, welfare, and technological advancement.
3. To ensure robust and sustainable socio-economic progress, Georgia must capitalize on its strategic geographical position. This entails active participation in initiatives like the Europe-Caucasus-Asia Transport Corridor (TRACECA) and other significant international endeavors, including the development of maritime-ferry connections and deep-water ports endowed with favorable hydro-meteorological conditions.
4. Attaining candidate status within the European Union should be deemed a paramount objective of Georgia's governance apparatus across all levels. Fostering economic and political collaboration with EU member states should be accorded primacy on the national agenda.

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